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Entropy is latent heat

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Abstract

An attempt to explain the physical sense of entropy in thermodynamics is given here. It is shown that previous results of the author on the subject are partly correct.

Keywords: Enthalpy, temperature, Clausius' hypothesis, compression, heat capacity

1. Introduction

The physical sense of entropy in thermodynamics is still unknown. Therefore, the task to find a suitable explanation of entropy is still actual. In ^[1] it was obtained that entropy is the total heat contained in a substance and enthalpy is the total heat contained in the substance. However, this result has a disadvantage: entropy and heat must have different dimensions.

2. Theory

Let us consider compression of a substance.

$$PdV = \delta A \quad (1)$$

Here pressure P is the motive force of the process, δA is the effect: the work done by the motive force.

Analogously, for heat exchange at $P=\text{Const}$ one can write:

$$dQ = dU + PdV = dH \quad (2)$$

Here dQ is a quantity of heat introduced into the substance and dH is a change in the enthalpy. One can rewrite Eq. (2) like this:

$$TdS = dQ \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) is analogous to Eq. (1). Here T is the motive force of the process and dQ is the effect. One can see that entropy is converted into heat under the action of an external force.

One can assume that entropy is a latent heat which can turn into real heat under the action of a driving force. So, entropy is the total latent heat contained in the substance.

The results of ^[2] confirm the conclusions of ^[1]: enthalpy is the total heat contained in the substance. It supports the Clausius' hypothesis: "enthalpy denotes the heat actually present in the body..." In ^[3] it was shown that

$$S = \frac{H}{T_{\text{mean}}} \quad (4)$$

Where T_{mean} is the mean temperature of the interval between 0 and T° . Here T° is the temperature of standard conditions. One can note that in ^[4] it was found that

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$$H_i = CT_i \quad (5)$$

where H_i is “the heat needed to raise a substance from 0 K to the temperature T_i and C is “the average heat capacity in the interval from 0 to T_i .”

3. Conclusion

The results obtained in ^[1] are partly correct: the entropy of a substance is indeed the total heat contained in the substance; however, it is the latent heat but not the normal heat. The enthalpy of a substance is the total normal heat contained in the substance.

4. Funding sources and Conflict of Interest

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5. Data Availability Statement (DAS)

The data used to generate the results in the paper are available from the author upon a reasonable request.

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